

COHOMOLOGY OF LOW-DEMINSIONAL SCHRÖDINGER ALGEBRA S_n

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Cohomology of some algebraic structures (e.g. associative, Lie, commutative algebras) plays a key role in the study of deformations and extensions of algebras [2,3]. They are also useful in representation theory, category theory, differential geometry of Lie groups, homotopy algebras and quantization of Poisson manifolds in mathematical physics. In the last twenty years, cohomology theory has been formulated for various algebras including algebras over binary quadratic operads and combinatorial Loday-type algebras.

The Schrödinger Lie group describes symmetries of the free particle Schrödinger equation, see [5]. For any positive integer n , the Lie algebra S_n in $n + 1$ –dimensional space-time of the Schrödinger Lie group is called the Schrödinger algebra, see [2]. The Schrödinger algebra S_n is a non-semisimple Lie algebra and also plays an important role in theoretical physics. Recently there was a series of papers on studying the structure and representation theory and (bi)derivations of the Schrödinger algebra [1, 2, 6].

In the present work we consider cohomology of S_n in case of $n = 1, 2$ and 3 .

Definition 1. An algebra L over a field F is called Lie algebra if for any $x, y, z \in L$ the following identities

$$[x, [y, z]] + [y, [z, x]] + [z, [x, y]] = 0,$$

$$[x, x] = 0,$$

hold.

Let L be a Lie algebra. We denote the Lie bracket on L by $[\cdot, \cdot]_L$. A representation of the Lie algebra L is a vector space V together with a linear map (called the action map) $\rho: L \rightarrow \text{End}(V)$ satisfying

$$\rho([x, y]_L) = \rho(x) \circ \rho(y) - \rho(y) \circ \rho(x), \text{ for } x, y \in L$$

We denote a representation as above simply by V when the action map is clear from the context. Note that any Lie algebra L is a representation of itself with the action map $\rho: L \rightarrow \text{End}(L)$ given by $\rho(x)(y) = [x, y]_L$, for $x, y \in L$. This is called the adjoint representation.

Given a Lie algebra L and a representation V there is a cochain complex (called the Chevalley-Eilenberg cochain complex) $\{C^*(L, V), \delta\}$ where $C^n(L, V) = Hom(\wedge^n L, V)$ for $n \geq 0$ and the differential $\delta: C^n(L, V) \rightarrow C^{n+1}(L, V)$ given by

$$(\delta f)(x_1, \dots, x_{n+1}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n+1} (-1)^{i+1} \rho(x_i) f(x_1, \dots, \overline{x_i}, \dots, x_{n+1}) + \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n+1} (-1)^{i+j} f([x_i, x_j], x_1, \dots, \overline{x_i}, \dots, \overline{x_j}, \dots, x_{n+1}),$$

for $f \in C^n(L, V)$ and $x_1, \dots, x_{n+1} \in L$. Since the deriviate operator $d = \sum_{i \geq 0} d^i$

satisfies the property $d \circ d = 0$ the n -cohomology group is well defined and $HL^n(L, V) = ZL^n(L, V) / BL^n(L, V)$, where the elements $ZL^n(L, V)$ and $BL^n(L, V)$ are called n -cocycles and n -coboundaries, respectively.

The elements $f \in BL^2(L, L)$ and $\varphi \in ZL^2(L, L)$ are defined as follows

$$f(x, y) = [d(x), y] + [x, d(y)] - d([x, y]) \text{ for some linear map } d$$

and

$$(\delta^2 \varphi)(x, y, z) = [x, \varphi(y, z)] - [y, \varphi(x, z)] + [z, \varphi(x, y)] - \varphi([x, y], z) + \varphi([x, z], y) - \varphi([y, z], x) = 0$$

A 2-cocycle is called infinitesimal deformation.

Definition 2. The Schrödinger algebra S_n is a Lie algebra with a $\square$ -basis $e, f, h, z, x_i, y_i, s_{jk} (= -s_{kj}), 1 \leq i \leq n, 1 \leq j < k \leq n$ equipped with the following non-trivial commutation relations

$$[e, f] = h, [h, e] = 2e, [f, h] = 2f,$$

$$[x_i, y_i] = z, [h, x_i] = x_i, [h, y_i] = -y_i,$$

$$[e, y_i] = x_i, [f, x_i] = y_i,$$

$$[s_{jk}, x_i] = \delta_{ki} x_j - \delta_{ji} x_k, [s_{jk}, y_i] = \delta_{ki} y_j - \delta_{ji} y_k,$$

$$[s_{jk}, s_{lm}] = \delta_{lk} s_{jm} + \delta_{jm} s_{kl} + \delta_{mk} s_{lj} + \delta_{lj} s_{mk},$$

where δ_{ij} is the Kronecker Delta defined as 1 for $i = j$ and as 0 otherwise.

Proposition 1. The dimension of the second coboundary space of Schrödinger algebra S_n is equal to:

$$\dim BL^2(S_n, S_n) = \begin{cases} 30, & n = 1, \\ 71, & n = 2, \\ 156, & n = 3. \end{cases}$$

Proposition 2. The dimension of the second cocycle space and cohomology of Schrödinger algebra S_n are equal to:

$$\dim ZL^2(S_n, S_n) = \begin{cases} 30, & n = 1, \\ 73, & n = 2, \\ 156, & n = 3, \end{cases} \quad \dim HL^2(S_n, S_n) = \begin{cases} 0, & n = 1, \\ 2, & n = 2, \\ 0, & n = 3. \end{cases}$$

Theorem. The equivalence classes $\overline{\varphi_1}, \overline{\varphi_2}$ forms a basis of $HL^2(S_2, S_2)$, where

$$\varphi_1(s_{12}, z) = z, \quad \varphi_1(s_{12}, x_1) = \frac{1}{2}x_1, \quad \varphi_1(s_{12}, x_2) = \frac{1}{2}x_2, \quad \varphi_1(s_{12}, y_1) = \frac{1}{2}y_1, \quad \varphi_1(s_{12}, y_2) = \frac{1}{2}y_2,$$

$$\begin{cases} \varphi_2(x_2, x_1) = e, & \varphi_2(y_1, x_1) = \frac{3}{2}s_{12}, & \varphi_2(y_2, y_1) = -\frac{1}{2}h, \\ \varphi_2(y_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{2}h, & \varphi_2(y_2, x_2) = \frac{3}{2}s_{12}, & \varphi_2(y_2, y_1) = -f, \end{cases}$$

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